

NATO Security Policy – Georgian National Values

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ABSTRACT: After gaining the independence Georgia has made a choice in favor of democracy, which implies a great difficulty, risks, challenges and threats to a small state and demands adequate responses. The internal political processes of the country depend on changing situation of the international arena. The existing threats and challenges made it necessary to establish a fundamental document - National Security Concept, which would be based on the democratic course of Georgia, national values and the elaboration of effective security mechanisms for its own people. The important vector of security policy of Georgia is directed towards the integration of the North Atlantic Alliance and the EU integration and strengthening of foreign relations, for which various strategic actions are undertaken such as participation in security operations and bilateral or multilateral cooperation that reduces political and military risks and correlates with the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the country. Striving to NATO and finally, its membership ensures the spread of democratic values and Establishment of the supremacy of law. On the way to the integration of the Alliance - the form of democratic arrangement of the state is one of the main prerequisites. Georgia is gradually improving the country's political environment in order to achieve this goal to maintain stability and to support the supremacy of law, which is the cornerstone of democracy.

KEYWORDS: North Atlantic Alliance, Security Concept, National Values, Security System, Spread of Democracy

Georgia locates in an important geographical area, which strategically has been principal for centuries in military, economic and political terms, which increases the issue of strengthening the security of the country.

After gaining independence from the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, Georgia continued to move towards democracy, which led to the annexation of the neighboring state and made it necessary for the country to develop the national security concept. The first steps towards the development of this concept were taken in 2004, G. Bezhuashvili was instructed to create a document based on Georgia's democratic course, national values and the development of effective mechanisms to protect the security of its people (Georgian Parliament's Resolution on the Development of the National Security Concept, №484–II, October 12, 2004). It was done through the Office of the Security Council in cooperation with the Ministries.

This fundamental document reflects the changes and impacts that have taken place in the field of security on the country, the threats, the risks, the challenges, and the adequate response.

It has great importance to changing the situation in the international arena for the security of Georgia and effects on the internal political processes of the state. The achievement of a democratic state, which needs to be strengthened through reforms.

Georgia needs to establish partnerships with each state and the Union of States, especially with the European Union and the United States, which has supported the country's regional stability since the day democracy was achieved. The great attention is

paid to national values, the country's sovereignty and territorial integrity, freedom, democracy and the rule of law, security, prosperity, and peace.

Ensuring the security of the country is a unified national responsibility, that is why the country's national values need to be in line with the country's foreign policy and military strategies. It is important to consider Georgia's national values in terms of compatibility with NATO. As you know, security challenges are the priority for the Alliance, that is why the appropriate programs are being developed which is tailored to the country's national security challenges.

Sovereignty and territorial integrity – It ranks first in the Georgian national values. After gaining independence in 1991, Georgian has chosen in favour of democracy. From the marked period made a start Georgia's entry in the international arena, where the country sought guarantees of sovereignty. At the Prague Summit in 1992, the President of Georgia Eduard Shevardnadze announced for the first time the integration into NATO. Since that time, Georgia has been working closely with NATO, which is funded by the Alliance's proposed programs.

Georgia's aspiration to become a member of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization stems from security policy. Due to Georgia's geopolitical location, maintaining the country's sovereignty and territorial integrity faces constant challenges that are threatened by Russia's expansionist policies. The pursuit of NATO and the special programs proposed by the Alliance reduce the political and military risks associated with the country's sovereignty and territorial integrity.

Freedom – The second national value occupies a special place in the history of Georgia and is characterized by complex dynamics. The history of Georgia's freedom does not begin in 1991, and it has deeper historical roots. Ensuring freedom was a precondition for the formation of NATO in 1949, which was directed against the expansionist policies of the Soviet Union. NATO's enlargement policy has been to ensure and maintain the security of the territories liberated from Soviet clutches. NATO was the guarantee of the independence of the liberated countries, which is ensured by Article 5 of the North Atlantic Treaty. As for political freedom, the fundamental value for NATO is democracy and freedom, which is reflected in the rule of law. The freedom of each individual is a constitutional guarantee in NATO member states.

Democracy and rule of law – The pursuit of NATO and, ultimately, its membership ensures the spread of democratic values and the establishment of the rule of law. One of the main prerequisites for the formation of a democratic organization on the path is the integration into the Alliance. To achieve this goal, Georgia is gradually improving the country's political environment to maintain stability and support the rule of law, which is the cornerstone of democracy. In the Threat Assessment Document of Georgia, we read that ensuring Georgia's security means creating and maintaining a favorable environment for the peaceful, democratic development of the country and the maximum realization of the national interests, as well as ensuring the physical security of each citizen, their rights and freedoms and equal opportunities. Alliance initiatives related to greater strategic security are saturated with the theory of democratic peace, according to which Democrats do not fight each other, and universal goodness is achieved based on three basic principles: dominance, reciprocity, and identity.

Security – To ensure long-term strategic security, the Alliance is implementing programs in Georgia that are tailored to the country's situation. Martin Edmond's definition of the national security system is the most indicative of the scale of NATO's programs. According to him, the operative functions of the national security system are performed by the armed forces, the police, a few public institutions in functional

relation with them (fire protection, border protection, customs). Besides, the security system includes decision-making and administrative institutions: the government or its special committees. (Edmonds 2004). NATO is conducting educational training in Georgia, which also aims to develop employees in the field of defence and other security. Also noteworthy are the programs implemented to increase the country's defence capabilities and their relation to national security. In addition to security guarantees, the process of rapprochement with NATO and ultimately its accession contributes to the establishment of the rule of law, the reduction of risks and external effects, economic development, which in turn ensures stability.

Prosperity – Economic Policy Research Center (EPRC) has prepared a report about „The Effect of NATO”. The report analyzes foreign experience and the potential effect of NATO.

- ✓ GDP - increased by about 1.5 times immediately.
- ✓ Foreign direct investment – increased approximately 3 times.
- ✓ Unemployment – reduced by about 3 times.
- ✓ Life expectancy – increased by an average of 5 years.
- ✓ Regional integration – exports and imports have doubled.

The economic efficiency of a nation depends on ensuring long-term security and stability. NATO membership provides security, which is a source of financial stability and promotes economic growth.

Peace – Reducing political risk and ultimately eliminating it, which accompanies NATO and ensures peace. In the Article 2 of the Washington Treaty states, “The Parties shall promote the development of friendly and peaceful international relations by strengthening independent institutions, raising awareness of the basic principles of these institutions and promoting stability and prosperity. The parties seek to remove obstacles to their international economic policies and to promote economic cooperation. ”

NATO-Georgia relations and the country's national security are characterized by challenges in Georgia. As a result of the 2008 Russia-Georgia war, the country experienced a crisis which was characterized by exceptional severity. As you know, after 2008 a secret embargo was imposed on Georgia and we became victims of the information war in the international arena. Russia is constantly trying to accuse Georgia of starting a war and genocide, as well as trying to portray Georgia as - an undemocratic state. However, as a result of the 2014 Russia-Ukraine war, NATO's focus has changed significantly.

Both NATO and the European Union are reviewing their policies and maintaining/strengthening their collective defence capabilities to curb aggression. The Western state understands the risks that Russia's aggressive policy poses to democratic ideologies. Besides, NATO is expanding its cooperation with partner countries to deter Russia from facilitating the process of their integration into the Alliance. This process may be called the New Truman Doctrine, which still serves the purpose of restraining Russia's expansive goals and is aimed at strengthening NATO allies.

Conclusions

Georgia's national security depends largely on NATO's security policy. As a result of cooperation with NATO, the security environment in Georgia has been improved, which is provided by special programs of the Alliance. Also, the aspiration for NATO for Georgia is a policy of restraint, which is determined by the absence of possible potential military aggression by Russia. Under such conditions, Georgia is given the opportunity to maintain the values enshrined in the National Security Concept and

increase its defence capabilities. As we have already mentioned, security is a common national responsibility and NATO is a reliable partner of Georgia in the process of building a country and maintaining its sovereignty.

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